

Adoption of e-learning technology by digital low-skilled teachers in higher education

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ABSTRACT

This research provides insights into what success factors digital low-skilled teachers can utilize in order to adopt e-learning technology in the curriculum of their universities. As a result, the following research question is formulated:

“What are the critical success factors that have an impact on the adoption of e-learning technology for teachers that are digitally low-skilled in higher education?”

To respond to this question, quantitative data is collected through a questionnaire, which is sent to several universities in the Netherlands and neighboring countries. In addition, the UTAUT model is used to demonstrate the relations between the main variables; perceived ease of use, social influence, perceived usefulness and digital competences. The research demonstrates that the variable ‘perceived usefulness’ is the only valid predictor for the adoption of e-learning technology.

To conclude, this research fits into the track ‘working and studying from home’ of this year’s academic conference (TUoDX), COVID-19 and the digital transformation.

Keywords

E-learning technology, teaching, digital competence, UTAUT.

INTRODUCTION

During the COVID-19 crisis (March 2020 - Present), higher education has switched from on-campus teaching to teaching via e-learning technology. Students are forced to study from home and teachers must set up a room to record their lessons in order to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus. “The term e-learning technology is widely

understood to refer to the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in learning and teaching (Czerniewicz & Brown, 2009; Salmon, 2005)”.

Educational institutions have invested heavily in e-learning technology to facilitate remote teaching. In recent months, e-learning technology has been on the rise (Oxford Business Group, 2020). This market has been projected to grow at a rate of 14 percent annually between 2019 and 2025 (PR Newswire, 2020).

Scull, Phillips, Sharma, and Garnier (2020) have focused on the adoption of e-learning within universities and its impact on students and their learning curve. Therefore, in this research, the focus is set on the target audience ‘teachers employed in higher education’. This entails universities of applied sciences and research universities. This paper was carried out based on literature concerning barriers perceived by teachers to the adoption of e-learning technology, as published in three databases: ScienceDirect, Scopus and Google Scholar.

The data has been collected via a digital survey that has been distributed in universities in the Netherlands and different neighboring countries.

The aim of this research is to gain knowledge about digitally low-skilled teachers and their adoption of e-learning technologies in higher education. This is based on the factors that influence the adoption of e-learning: perceived ease of use (effort expectancy), social influence, and perceived usefulness (performance expectancy) (Decman, 2015).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the development of new e-learning technology to facilitate the transition from offline to online education, adaptation by both students and teachers needs to be considered. In contrast to students, tend to struggle more to keep up with advancements in e-learning technology. This is mainly due to teachers lacking time to learn how to use the technology (Dornisch, 2013).

As a result, this may impact different areas. For example, the quality of the lessons can be positively influenced by the correct use of e-learning technology. Using the right e-learning skills, teachers can make sure that students are stimulated during the lessons (Alsabawy et al., 2016, p. 848).

Current literature focuses on the student versus teacher perspective on the adoption of e-learning technology and its impact on students. (Paechter et al., 2010, p. 227; Park et al., 2011, p. 597) The perspective of the teachers remains underexposed. Hence, this research is solely focused on the teacher's perspective.

Central to the teacher perspective is the ability to use e-learning technology considering the consequences of the ongoing digital transformation for a specific group of teachers. Teachers with a high digital competence will thrive in this transformation, while digitally low-skilled teachers may struggle using e-learning technologies. This has to do with the ability to adapt to new technologies. Teachers who are less able to adapt may adhere to previous generations of methods, whereas teachers who adopt new technologies more easily may use these to fit into their learning strategy (Mohammadyari & Singh, 2014).

Previous research in the specific field of teacher adoption of e-learning technology mainly addressed the group of teachers that are digitally high-skilled teachers (Yuen & Ma, 2008). The respondents of the study by Yuen and Ma were limited to teachers in higher education who consider themselves intermediate or upper-intermediate in computing skills. Besides, 80 percent of those respondents fall within the age group of 25 to 35. Therefore, this research is considered not representative for the whole teacher population, because approximately 9 percent of the teachers worldwide in higher education are 30 years or younger. In contrast, 41 percent of the teachers are 50 years or older (OECD, 2018).

Consequently, the knowledge gap that has been discovered is that existing literature falls short in exploring the factors leading to increased adoption of e-learning technologies for the target

group of this research: teachers that are digitally low-skilled.

In order to address this knowledge gap, this research aims to examine what critical success factors digitally low-skilled teachers may utilize in order to adopt e-learning technology. This research provides an understanding of how digitally low-skilled teachers can bridge the digital divide towards their higher skilled counterparts.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The previous section has made clear that this research will focus on the main factors that impact the adoption of e-learning technology by teachers in higher education who are digitally low-skilled in. The sub-questions are formulated to jointly answer the main research question:

"What factors have an impact on the adoption of e-learning technology for digital low-skilled teachers in higher education?"

Sub-questions

1. What is e-learning technology?
2. What is the definition of digital competence?
3. How is e-learning technology currently perceived by digitally low-skilled teachers employed in higher education?
4. To what extent does digital competence play a role in the adoption of e-learning technology?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

From the questions answered in this section it can be concluded that the terms e-learning technology, digital competences and lower digital skills play an important role in the research. These key concepts are explained in more detail.

What is e-learning technology?

The concept of e-learning technology is central to the research carried out. In doing so, “e-learning technology” has the following meaning: e-learning systems are a major application of IT in educational organizations. There is no uniform view on e-learning systems (Alshawaby, 2016). According to Welsh, Wanberg, Brown, and Simmering (2003) “e-learning can be defined as the use of computer network technology, primarily over an intranet or through the internet, to deliver information and instruction to individuals.”

What is the definition of digital competence and digital skills?

Digital competence

There are several frameworks defining teachers' ICT competences and their professional uses (e.g., UNESCO, 2011; ISTE-T, 2017). These frameworks generally include four areas: technological appropriation, pedagogical practice, academic administration and evaluation, and teacher development.

Digital skills

According to Van Laar et al. (2020) digital skills are defined as: “(1) the mastery of ICT applications to solve cognitive tasks at work; (2) skills that are not technology-driven, as they do not refer to the use of any particular software program; (3) skills that support higher-order thinking processes; and (4) skills related to cognitive processes favoring employees' continuous learning”.

RELEVANCE

Managerial Relevance

As the importance of e-learning technology increases in the curriculums, the findings of the research may be used by tertiary educational institutions to foster adoption of e-learning technologies by digitally low-skilled teachers.

Academic Relevance

The purpose of this research is to build on current literature in the field of adoption of e-learning technology in research universities and universities of applied sciences. Previous research focused on adaptation of e-learning tools for primary and secondary school teachers (Hrtonová, Kohout, Rohlíková, & Zounek, 2014).

Other recent research focused on the student's perspective in Australian universities of e-learning technology (Scull, Phillips, Sharma, & Garnier, 2020). This research, however, generates new insights into the impact of the factors that influence the use of technology for digitally low-skilled teachers in tertiary education. This research may form a basis for further research in the e-learning educational environment.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)-model is used to demonstrate the relations between the main variables in this research (Venkatesh, Morris, Davis & Davis, 2012).

Based on current literature in the field of adoption of e-learning technology, the independent variables (IV) ‘perceived ease of use’, ‘social influence’ and ‘perceived usefulness’ affect the dependent variable ‘adoption of e-learning technology’ through the mediating variable ‘behavioral intention’. Behavioral intention is defined as ‘habit is the tendency to automatically use technology as a result of learned behavior’ (Venkatesh et al., 2012). The relationship between the three independent variables and the mediating variable moderated by ‘digital competence’ and ‘attitude’ (Decman, 2015; Koohang, 1989; Violato, Mariniz & Hunter, 1989).

The independent variable ‘perceived ease of use’ can be defined as “the degree of ease associated with the use of the system” (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p.450). In the literature, perceived ease of use is also referred to as performance expectancy. Perceived ease of use influences behavioral intention (Davis, 1989). Hence the first hypothesis is: *H1: Perceived ease of use influences the behavioral intention to use e-learning technology.*

Social influence is the variable of “the degree to which an individual perceives that important others believe he or she should use the new system” (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p. 451) is the second determinant of the behavioral intention to use a technique or technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Social influence affects behavioral intention, because “it is important to note that social influence in technology adoption is crucial amongst teachers” (Taylor & Todd, 1995; Venkatesh & Davis, 1996).

Kreijns, Van Acker, Vermeulen and Van Buuren (2012) concluded that “if low self-efficacy teachers see that even their colleagues who are perceived as not capable to use ICT are successfully using digital learning materials, then those reluctant teachers may become convinced that they were wrong about their judgments of their own capacity to use digital learning materials”. As a result, their self-efficacy may get a boost. The latter phenomenon is reflected in the phrase ‘If even they can do it, I certainly can do it’. The fact that colleagues are using digital learning materials may also improve the teachers’ attitude towards using digital learning materials. It is argued that teachers may think that if so, many colleagues are using digital learning materials, then there must be something good in it, otherwise they would not use it. The second hypothesis is therefore formulated as follows: *H2: Social influence affects behavioral intention.*

Perceived usefulness is defined as “the degree to which the user expects that using the system will help him or her to attain gains in job performance” (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p. 447). In literature this IV is also referred to as effort expectancy. Perceived usefulness influences behavior intention, because Gressard and Loyd (1985) concluded that “the perceived usefulness of computers can influence attitudes towards computers and the amount of confidence a teacher possesses in using computers may influence his or her implementation in the classroom”. Therefore, the third hypothesis is *H3: Teachers’ level of perceived usefulness of e-learning usage influences their satisfaction with e-learning usage.*

Behavioral intention is a valid predictor of adoption of technology, according to Venkatesh (2003). Prior studies have stated that teachers’ attitudes as well as knowledge and skills in using computers are major factors affecting their initial acceptance of computer technology and moreover their future behavior regarding computer usage (Koohang, 1989; Violato, Mariniz & Hunter, 1989). Adoption is ‘the process whereby the users first become aware of the technology until the user makes full use of the technology’ (Renaud & van Bijon, 2008). Thus, the fourth hypothesis is *H4: Teachers’ behavioral intention influences the adoption of e-learning technology.*

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

METHOD

The used research method is quantitative descriptive research. As such, the research strategy is a survey. The survey, in the form of a questionnaire, was conducted to find answers to the defined research questions and to test the hypotheses.

A questionnaire allows the collection of data about the selected topic from a large number of people in a cost- and time-effective manner. Moreover, it enables to obtain subjective measures when observation of the participants is not feasible. Lastly, comparison of the gathered responses is possible by using standardized questions (Saunders, Lewis, 2017).

The survey was distributed in the personal networks of the researchers through different digital channels, such as LinkedIn and email. The population consists of all teachers that are employed in higher education, specifically universities of applied sciences and research universities.

Two non-probability sampling designs, snowball sampling and convenience sampling, are used, due to the lack of an adequate sampling frame (Sekaran, Bougie, 2016).

Measurement procedure and instruments

The questionnaire was based on the adoption of e-learning technology (Sørebø et al., 2009, p. 1186). It also reflected specific aspects of the teachers and the behavioral intention, including the perceived ease of use of the e-learning technology. The first part of the questionnaire was focused on general characteristics in order to determine the background of respondents. The second part consists of nine statements and examines their e-learning experience and their motivation and expectations. The data was collected in a time frame of ten working days.

Teachers in the personal networks of the researchers were approached to fill out an online questionnaire that was created through the online tool 'Qualtrics'. The participants were assured that their responses would be handled in a confidential manner.

The dependent variable and the independent variables were measured on a five-point Likert-scale. This scale is generally treated as an interval measurement scale, hence the strongest inferential statistical technique, multiple regression analysis, was selected (Sekaran, Bougie, 2016).

Appendix I provides an overview of the questions asked in the online questionnaire with the corresponding source and measurement scale.

Respondents

The sample size should be ten or more times as large as the number of variables in the study in multivariate research (Roscoe, 1975). Hence the projected sample size should be at least 75 respondents.

Validity

The variables perceived ease of use, social influence, perceived usefulness and behavioral intention were adapted from several high-quality research papers in order to establish high validity. (e.g. Sjørebø, 2009; McGill, 2014). Moreover, multi-item measurements were used to ensure that considerable conceptual overlap exists between the measures and the constructs. Lastly, the questions were phrased in an unbiased way, by avoiding leading and loading questions (Saunders & Lewis, 2017).

To check if the set of items are interrelated by checking the correlation between the given item and the sum if the given item is not included in the scale. This is considered the internal validity. Lower values (below 0.3) indicate the given item does not correlate to the others. In contrast, higher values (above 0.3), indicate that the given item correlates to the others (Sekaran & Bougie 2016).

Reliability

The reliability was measured with Cronbach's alpha that lies between 0 and 1. A Cronbach's alpha of at least 0.7 is considered a good level of reliability (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

To ensure high quality in this paper, off-the-shelf questions from Sjørebø (2009) and McGill (2014) were used.

This paper was carried out based on literature published in three databases, ScienceDirect, Scopus and Google Scholar, concerning barriers to the adoption of e-learning technology as perceived by teachers.

A literature review was used to determine the measurements for the adoption of e-learning technology and digitally low-skilled teachers in higher education. High-quality articles are used to significantly increase the reliability of each measurement (Sekaran, & Bougie, 2016).

RESULTS

A total of 49 survey responses (n= 49) were received. However, three responses were incomplete. Therefore, the final sample size is 46 (n = 46).

Nearly 80% of the respondents are employed in universities of applied sciences; 20 percent are employed in research universities.

Concerning geographical location, 87.8% of the respondents are located in the Netherlands. A small minority, 12.3%, are located in other countries, including Germany, Belgium and Canada.

Looking at the age groups, 27.1% of the respondents fall within the age category 40 – 49, followed by around 20% in each of the other age categories. There are no respondents from the age group 70 years or older.

A large majority of 91.3% agrees to the statement that e-learning technology is useful in their classes. However, only 63.3% is satisfied with the overall experience of e-learning technology.

Similarly, 60.8% agrees or somewhat agrees that their first experience with e-learning technology exceeded their expectations. Moreover, 47.9% of respondents either disagree or neither agree nor disagree whether the service level of e-learning technology has been better than they expected, whereas 52.1% agrees or somewhat agrees.

Furthermore, 84.8% agrees or somewhat agrees that they could improve their digital skills to use e-learning technology. The answers to the statement 'management supported the idea of using e-learning technology before the COVID-19 crisis' are almost equally divided. Subsequently, a small majority of 56.5% finds that their colleagues

supported them in their use of e-learning technology.

60.9% agrees or somewhat agrees there are sufficient training possibilities to use e-learning technology efficiently. Lastly, only 8.7% does not intend to use e-learning technology after education will return to on-campus teaching.

In addition to the correlation measurements, Cronbach's Alpha is also measured for the variables with multi-item measurements. Cronbach's Alpha of Perceived usefulness is 0.564, Perceived ease of use is 0.621, whereas Social influence is 0.540.

The table below shows the unstandardized and standardized coefficients, as well as the level of significance of the variables.

Table 1: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient Beta.	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Sig.
Constant	1.890	-	0.71
Perceived ease of use	-.269	-0.185	0.298
Perceived usefulness	0.560	0.454	0.006
Social influence	0.129	0.124	0.408
Digital competence	0.159	0.132	0.417

DISCUSSION

First of all, to gather data about the population, snowball sampling and convenience sampling designs are used to get an indication of the user behavior towards the adoption of e-learning technology. These sampling methods are in general inexpensive and little time consuming.

However, a main disadvantage of these non-probability sampling designs is that the participants are not representative of the population. This results in a low generalizability of this research.

The requirement for a survey is that the sample must be higher than 75 respondents. However, in this survey the sample size is 46 respondents. Therefore, this requirement is not met.

Valid conclusions of the population using this low sample size can therefore not be drawn.

As for the correlation between the independent

variables and behavioral intention, a correlation above 0.3 is considered acceptable. Therefore, the following can be concluded. First of all, the correlation between perceived ease of use and behavioral intention is 0.116. Hence, the increase in perceived ease of use has almost no influence on the increase of behavioral intention. This can also be presumed about the social influence and digital competence, having correlations of respectively 0.159 and 0.173. On the contrary, a perceived usefulness of 0.435 indicates a strong positive correlation and is the only significant variable at a level of 0.003.

Secondly, when it comes to reliability, it is important that Cronbach's Alpha is at least 0.70. Looking at the reliability of the multiple-item measures to determine the constructs, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.564 for the variable Perceived usefulness is, 0.621 for Perceived ease of use, and 0.540 for Social influence 0.540. As a result, it can be concluded that each construct has a low interrelatedness since they fall below the threshold of 0.7.

Thirdly, the coefficient of determination (R²), confirms that 21.9% of the variation of the model (at a significance level of 0.035) is explained by the variables included in this research.

Lastly, the research demonstrates that the variable perceived usefulness is the only valid predictor for the adoption of e-learning technology. However, the reliability of this multi-item construct is slightly lower than preferred (0.564 < 0.7). Consequently, there is not enough statistical evidence that the other variables in this research are reliable predictors of adoption of e-learning technology.

CONCLUSION

This research examined the predictors of the adoption of e-learning technology by teachers. However, the results are not statistically significant, except for the variable 'perceived usefulness'. Thus, this variable forms the only valid predictor in this research. In other words, an experience with e-learning technology that is satisfactory or deemed to be useful increases its adoption.

A number of limitations are identified in this research. Firstly, the use of non-probability sampling designs and the small sample size decrease the generalizability of the findings. Secondly, most of the respondents lived in the Netherlands. As a result, the sample does not represent the population worldwide. Thirdly, the amount of multi-item measurements should be expanded to ensure that the measurements overlap with the abstract constructs of the conceptual model.

In future research, it would be relevant to further study the adoption of e-learning by teachers, with consideration of internal factors, such as motivation and attitude, in order to identify the root cause. Because this research mainly focused on the Netherlands, it would be relevant to examine whether results in other countries differ from those from the Netherlands. In short, this would make it possible to see whether the adoption of e-learning technology in higher education in other countries is significantly better. It could then turn out that the difference in adoption of e-learning technology by teachers may be due to other factors that are not examined in the present research. Therefore, conducting international research is recommended.

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APPENDIX I: SURVEY QUESTIONS

Type of measurement: 5-point Likert-scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3= neither agree nor disagree, 4 = somewhat agree, 5 = agree) for the nine statements.

Source:

- Off the shelf, Sjørebø et al., 2009, p. 1186
- Off the shelf, McGill et al., 2014, p. 33

Table 2: Survey

Construct name	Measurement
General	Close-ended questions. Age, type of university, country, field of study.
Close-ended Statements	
Behavioral intention	1. I intend to use E-learning tools after education could return to on-campus education.
Perceived usefulness	2. I find E-learning technology to be useful in my classes.
Perceived usefulness	3. I am satisfied with my overall experience of E-learning technology.
Perceived ease of use	4. My first experience with E-learning technology was better than I expected.
Perceived ease of use	5. The service level of the E-learning technology was better than I expected.
Digital competence	6. I could improve my skills by using E-learning technology.
Perceived ease of use	7. My management supported the idea of using E-learning technology, before the COVID-19 crisis.
Social influence	8. My colleagues support me when I am having issues with E-learning technology.
Social influence	9. I feel like there are sufficient training possibilities to use E-learning technology.